

The NOAA JPSS Satellite Program and Applications

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NOAA/JPSS

INTRODUCTION

The Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS) consists of a suite of five instruments: advanced microwave and infrared sounders critical for short and medium range weather forecasting; an advanced visible and infrared imager needed for environmental assessments such as snow/ice cover, droughts, volcanic ash, forest fires and surface temperature; ozone sensor primarily used for global monitoring of ozone and input to weather and climate models; and an earth radiation budget sensor for monitoring the Earth's energy budget. JPSS is implemented through a partnership between the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and the US National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). NOAA is responsible for overall funding; maintaining the high-level requirements; establishing international and interagency partnerships; developing the science and algorithms, and user engagement; NOAA also provides product data distribution and archiving of JPSS data. NASA's role is to serve as

acquisition Center of Excellence, providing acquisition of instruments, spacecraft and the multi-mission ground system, and early mission implementation through turnover to NOAA for operations (Goldberg et al., 2013). The observatory nadir deck incorporates: the Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite (OMPS) instrument built by BATC, Boulder, Colorado; Advance Technology Microwave Sounder (ATMS) built by Northrop Grumman Electronic Systems (NGES) in Azusa, California; Cross-Track Infrared Sounder (CrIS), built by ITT Exelis in Ft. Wayne, Indiana; Clouds and Earth's Radiant Energy Sensor (CERES) built by Northrop Grumman Aerospace Systems (NGAS) in El Segundo, California; and the Visible-Infrared Imaging Suite (VIIRS), built by Raytheon Aerospace Systems in El Segundo, California. The JPSS is now being demonstrated by the Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (S-NPP), which essentially has the same instrumentation as JPSS-1. JPSS-1 is scheduled for launch in early 2017, followed by JPSS-2 in early 2022. S-NPP was launched in 2011.

Applications of satellite data are paramount to transform science and technology to product and services which are used in critical decision making. For the satellite community, good representations of technology are the satellite sensors, while science provides the instrument calibration and derived geophysical parameters. Weather forecasting is an application of the science and technology provided by remote sensing satellites. The Joint Polar Satellite System, which includes S-NPP provides formidable science and technology to support many applications and includes support to 1) weather forecasting – data from the JPSS CrIS and ATMS are used to forecast weather events out to 7 days - nearly 85% of all data used in weather forecasting are from polar orbiting satellites; 2) environmental monitoring -data from the JPSS VIIRS are used to monitor the environment including the health of coastal ecosystems, drought conditions, fire, smoke, dust, snow and ice, and the state of oceans, including sea surface temperature and ocean color; and 3) climate monitoring – data from JPSS instruments, including OMPS and CERES will provide continuity to climate data records established using NOAA POES and NASA Earth Observing System (EOS) satellite observations. To bridge the gap between products and applications, the JPSS Program has

established a proving ground program to optimize the use of JPSS data with other data sources to improve key products and services. A number of operational and research applications will be presented along with how the data and applications support a large number of societal benefit areas of the Global Earth Observation Systems of Systems (GEOSS).

THE JPSS PROVING GROUND PROGRAM

The JPSS Proving Ground (PG) Program involves key users within National Weather Service (NWS), National Ocean Service (NOS), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) and Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR). Major successes of this program included funding the activities, which enabled the very early assessment (beginning one month after launch) of ATMS observations in the (NWS) data assimilation system. Normally, a new instrument would require two years of software development and testing before the data can be used operationally in the NWS forecast models. However, with the NWS as part of the Cal/Val team with associated funding and working with NESDIS operations, the ATMS data became operational at NCEP in May 2012, breaking the record of assimilating a new instrument

by more than 16 months. The CrIS sounder data was assimilated shortly after the 2013 hurricane season software freeze was lifted. Another success area is the JPSS PG project leads ability to quickly engage users during rapidly changing environmental events to determine how they can redirect their PG project to assist these users in their response. Projects were able to provide important S-NPP data for such diverse events as Super Storm Sandy, the Colorado Rim Fire, the Yukon River Flooding in Alaska, and the South Platte River flooding in Colorado.

The JPSS PG Program's development of the Community Satellite Processing Package (CSPP) for direct readout capabilities has become a cornerstone of a number of PG Projects. In Alaska, CSPP minimizes the time from observation to the utilization of critical VIIRS imagery by weather forecasters to assess extreme weather events. The temporal frequency of S-NPP/JPSS data over Alaska is much greater because of its high latitude; hence the data is very important to nowcasting applications. International direct readout stations are using CSPP operationally. Proving ground projects include improving tropical storm forecasting both track and intensity using ATMS, VIIRS and CrIS data, exploiting VIIRS in Graphical Information Systems (GIS) to help the NMFS to monitor marine resources. VIIRS ocean color data are being

used in NOS to monitor coastal water quality. VIIRS data are being used to detect and monitor forest fires. Funding the exploitation of the VIIRS Day Night Band resulted in new discoveries, including demonstrating the use of VIIRS DNB for examining tropical storm structure at night for improved short term forecasting, and a recent discovery of applications of the DNB under moonless skies for meteorological applications (Miller et al., 2012).

The Proving Ground component consists of demonstration and utilization of data products by the end-user operational and/or research unit, such as one of the National Weather Service's (NWS) National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP), one or more NWS Weather Forecast Offices, and NOAA's Ecological Forecasting Roadmap and related activities, and Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR). The Proving Ground also promotes outreach, training, and coordination of new products with the end users, incorporating user feedback for product improvements. The Risk Reduction component mitigates potential risk in algorithms and data products by testing alternative algorithms and developing new research and applications to maximize the benefits of S-NPP/JPSS satellite data. Risk Reduction also encourages fusion of data/information

from multiple satellites, models, and in-situ data.

Since the formation of the JPSS PGRR program in 2011, the program has been very successful in providing resources to enable the use of S-NPP direct broadcast by the NWS, especially in Alaska and Hawaii. VIIRS imagery through direct readout is now routinely used by a number of weather forecast offices. Data portals providing easy access to VIIRS active fires, air quality and regional ocean color products were established. Improvements in tropical cyclone forecasting using ATMS and CrIS have been demonstrated. Support to global data assimilation showing the value of ATMS and CrIS were successful. JPSS PGRR supports education and training, direct readout infrastructure and airborne validation campaigns. Various NOAA user groups have determined priorities for JPSS PGRR. These include the JPSS PGRR Executive Board, the NWS Operational Advisory Team (NOAT), the Satellite Development Executive Board (SDEB) and the Independent Advisory Committee (IAC). These priorities are based on NOAA strategic plans.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the JPSS Proving Ground Program has been a huge success. The innovative use of S-NPP data and the full

integration of the user community ensured thorough evaluation of capabilities and rapid transition from research to operations. The JPSS Program's multi-year commitment to this program allows project teams to define a successful path to assist the user community in fully integrating new JPSS capabilities.

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